

Large-scale multiactor training and mentorship programme to ASSist people with physical impairments in energy povERTy

D3.1 Multi Language ASSERT E-learning Platform Moodle

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ABOUT ASSERT

The ASSERT project is a European initiative funded under the LIFE23-CETENERPOV framework, which will address the critical issue of energy poverty, particularly among people with physical disabilities.

The project goal is three-fold:

1. Ensure that policy makers at all levels of administrations, as well as energy practitioners and advisors, receive training on energy issues, including energy poverty, while fully accounting for the multidimensional nature of energy poverty and the broader context of clean energy transition.
2. Roll-out programmes to train front line workers on energy poverty and green energy solutions. Front-line workers to be trained include health and social care workers or other professionals who can help identify households inhabited by people with disabilities and experiencing energy poverty and provide them with advice and information on solutions to reduce energy consumption and access more affordable and innovative sources.
3. Offer targeted training courses for vulnerable households, including those with low digital skills. Such courses should enhance the energy and digital literacy awareness of households affected by energy poverty, enable them to better control their energy bills and actively participate in the clean and just energy transition.

ASSERT will focus on people with physical disabilities who often have higher energy needs and lower incomes and therefore are more susceptible to energy poverty and its effects. Addressing their needs can interrupt the vicious circle of aggravating health conditions because of unhealthy household conditions related to experiencing energy poverty.

The project will deliver an integrated target-specific training and mentorship programme for local policymakers and intermediaries and will equip them with essential skills and knowledge and support to implement sustainable energy solutions, while integrating energy poverty considerations into broader policy frameworks.

ASSERT consortium

N o	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	AISFOR SRL	AISFOR SRL	IT
2	RETE ASSIST - ETS	RETE ASSIST - ETS	IT
3	ENERCOOP	ENERCOOP	FR
4	ASOCIACION ECOSERVEIS	ECOSERVEIS	ES
5	CITIZEN CROSSROADS	CCR	EL
6	ENERGEIAKO GRAFEIO KYPROU	CEA	CY
7	CLIMATE ALLIANCE - KLIMA-BUENDNIS - ALIANZA DEL CLIMA e.V.	CLIMATE ALLIANCE	DE
8	EUROPEAN NETWORK ON INDEPENDENT LIVING BRUSSELS OFFICE	ENIL	BE
9	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	NTUA	EL
10	INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENERGY AND CLIMATE POLICY STICHTING	IEECP	NL
11	ACCADEMIA EUROPEA DI BOLZANO	Eurac	IT

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the **ASSERT Academy**, the multilingual e-learning platform developed within the ASSERT project to support the delivery of training programmes for municipalities and intermediary organisations. Built on the Moodle LMS system, the **ASSERT Academy serves as the central digital environment where all project-related training materials, tools, and resources are hosted in an organised, accessible, and user-friendly way**. Moreover, through the ASSERT Library, the platform also provides access to a curated selection of external training materials, reports and tools related to energy poverty, disability, gender, and energy efficiency.

This report outlines the **structure, architecture, and functionalities** of the platform, providing a clear and concise guide for users, illustrating each section with figures to support navigation and understanding. It explains how the Academy is organised into key sections, including:

1. The homepage.
2. The training courses section for municipalities and intermediaries.
3. Public deliverables.
4. The ASSERT Library.

Finally, the document examines the platform's accessibility features, explaining the standards adopted, the tools used to evaluate compliance, and the specific measures implemented to ensure that all learners, including those with disabilities, can use the platform effectively.

Overall, this report documents how the ASSERT Academy was designed to act as a **comprehensive, multilingual, and accessible training hub**, supporting the wider objectives of the ASSERT project to strengthen the capacity of policymakers and intermediaries.

1. ASSERT Academy: the e-learning platform

The ASSERT Academy is accessible online at the following link:

<https://assert.aisforacademy.eu/>.

The homepage will automatically open in one of the project languages (Catalan, Cypriot, English, French, Greek, Italian, Spanish) based on the user's location. If necessary, users can switch language on the upper right corner of the page. The various language packs were installed to make the platform fully accessible to stakeholders from all pilot countries, as well as other European regions. By enabling course delivery in multiple languages, including English, the platform removes linguistic barriers and ensures broader participation.

Figure 1: Homepage upper section

At the moment of the publication of this report, it includes the following public pages:

- Homepage
- ASSERT Official publications
- ASSERT Library

The registration page and the courses pages will also be made available publicly once the training materials for municipalities and intermediaries are finalised.

2. Platform Architecture

This section provides a brief, user-oriented overview of how to navigate ASSERT Academy.

The homepage is accessible by all users and requires no registration. As the ASSERT Academy will also be disseminated as a self-standing tool, the homepage must give users a general overview of the project and the training. For this reason, the following elements can be found on the homepage:

- Welcome to ASSERT: an overview of the project mission and targets.
- Our goals
- How we work
- ASSERT training courses are coming soon
- ASSERT Official publications
- ASSERT Library
- The pairs of involved municipalities and intermediaries: a section presenting the pairs of municipalities and intermediaries involved in each pilot country.
- ASSERT Energy Disability Policy Tracker
- About ASSERT: overview of the consortium partners
- Page footer, integrating the EU flag and funding acknowledgement statement, and linking the page to the piloting partners, coordinator, and other partners websites.

Our Goals

- Better understand the real needs of people with disabilities living in conditions of energy vulnerability.
- Improve local services, making them accessible, inclusive, and responsive to specific needs.
- Provide practical tools (guides, materials, consultations) to help families reduce energy costs and access available assistance more easily.
- Collect and analyze data to identify what truly works, guiding public policies and future interventions.

How we work

To achieve these goals, ASSERT is implementing a set of coordinated actions:

- Online training for municipal operators and intermediary organizations, with practical, easy-to-use content.
- Co-design meetings to jointly develop customized training tools and materials.
- Direct family support through home visits, energy kits, and personalized consultations.
- Exchange of experiences across participating territories, promoting good practices and innovative solutions.
- Impact evaluation through data collection and analysis before and after interventions, to adapt and improve actions.

Figure 2: Homepage midsection 1

ASSERT training courses are coming soon

Stay connected to our platform: soon you'll be able to access our training courses

ASSERT Official publications

Here you can find the official reports and publications issued within the project.

Enter

Discover the ASSERT Library

The ASSERT online library gathers resources on energy poverty and physical disability, providing useful materials for training, policies, and practical actions in a single accessible space.

Enter

Figure 3: Homepage midsection 2

The pairs of involved municipalities and intermediaries

The ASSERT project has involved 25 pairs of municipalities and intermediary organizations in a mentorship programme to develop specialized skills to address energy poverty, with a focus on supporting persons with physical impairments. Discover the involved municipalities and intermediaries!

Cyprus

1. Municipality of Nicosia and OPAK (Cyprus Paraplegic Organisation)
2. Municipality of Aradippou and KYSOA (Cyprus Confederation of Organisations for Disabilities)
3. Municipality of Athienou and SKE Athienou (Volunteers Council of Athienou)
4. Municipality of Ayia Napa and SMILE Project - Autism Support Famagusta
5. Municipality of Limassol and Pancyprian Association for the Rehabilitation of the Disabled (POAA) Limassol

France

1. City of Besançon (Energy Management Division) and APF France Handicap (Association of Paralyzed People of France) Bourgogne Franche-Comté
2. City of Paris (Ecological Transition and Climate Division Department) and XXX
3. Lille European Metropolis (Private Housing Department) and Inhai
4. Greater Lyon Metropolis (Safety, Health and Environment Department) and APF France Handicap (Association of Paralyzed People of France) AuvergneRhône-Alpes

Greece

1. Municipality of Komotini and Perpato Association
2. Municipality of Veroia and Ta paidia tis anoixis NGO
3. Municipality of Thessaloniki and Youth Council
4. Municipality of Athens and Sustainable Mobility Department of the Municipality's Urban Planning and Environment Directorate
5. Municipality of Kifisia and Community Center

Italy

1. Municipality of Parma and National Association of Families of People with Intellectual and/or Relational Disabilities - (ANFASS) – Parma
2. Municipality of Arezzo and Foundation Arezzo Comunità
3. Municipality of Sorrento and Caritas Sorrento
4. Municipio Rome I and CER Le Vele

Spain

1. Energy Advice Points of Barcelona City Council, Social Rights Area and Union of Mothers in Functional Diversity
2. Social Action Department of Igualada City Council and Auria Private Foundation
3. Disability Care Service and Energy Esplugues of Esplugues City Council and Esplugues Without Barriers
4. Valencia Foundation Climate and Energy and Cystic Fibrosis Association of the Valencian Community
5. Network for Climate Shelters Barcelona and Municipal Institute for People with Disabilities, and ECOM

Figure 4: Pairs of Involved Municipalities and Intermediaries

ASSERT Energy Disability Policy Tracker

The Energy Poverty and Disability Policy Tracker aims to be a one-stop shop for information on energy poverty mitigation measures and disability-related support policies. It includes policies at national and local level for five countries i.e., Italy, Cyprus, Greece, France, and Spain.

[Discover more!](#)

Figure 5: Energy Disability Policy Tracker

About ASSERT

ASSERT is a project funded by the European LIFE programme (LIFE23-CET-ASSERT) and coordinated by AISFOR.

Figure 6: Energy Disability Policy Tracker

Figure 7: Homepage Footer

3. ASSERT Training Courses

Two training courses, one for municipalities and one for intermediaries, will be offered in Catalan, Cypriot, English, French, Greek, Italian and Spanish, with users able to self-enroll in the language of their choice, through the platform dashboard.

Figure 8: Dashboard with courses for intermediaries and municipalities

The overall aim is to provide participants with the information, insights and practical skills required to effectively address energy poverty and deepen awareness of the specific challenges faced by people in situations of energy poverty and by persons with disabilities. Through these courses, users will strengthen their comprehensive understanding of energy poverty and the available solutions, ultimately improving the municipalities' capacity to integrate appropriate measures into local action plans, and the intermediaries' capacities to assist people in need.

The content of the courses will be adapted to the national contexts and will be structured around six main areas:

1. European and national regulatory frameworks on disability and energy poverty.
2. Energy poverty diagnosis.
3. The link between disability and energy poverty.
4. Practical and technical aspects of energy use and support mechanisms.
5. Inclusive communication.
6. Renewable energy use at the household level.

The platform will allow partners to keep track of the progress of the users in the course by analysing data on accesses.

4. ASSERT Official Publications

By entering the ASSERT Official publications section on the homepage, the user can find the project public deliverables and reports, linked to Zenodo.

Figure 9: Deliverables

5. ASSERT Library

By entering the ASSERT Library, the user can find a repository of training and educational resources currently available on energy poverty. A SWOT analysis has been conducted to evaluate and systematise the training and educational resources currently available in this section, with particular attention to how these resources incorporate, or fail to incorporate, the needs and perspectives of persons with disabilities. The assessment followed a rigorous multi-phase methodology combining qualitative and quantitative approaches. The process began with an extensive mapping of over forty training resources from EU projects, civil society, and institutional programmes, including both energy-poverty and disability-focused materials. A preliminary screening narrowed the selection to fifteen high-quality, highly relevant resources. These were then analysed through a detailed SWOT framework to capture both strengths and limitations, particularly regarding accessibility and intersectionality. The final phase translated the findings into operational decisions for inclusion in the ASSERT training library, classifying resources to keep, adapt, or only reference, supported by an additional accessibility check. The multi-phase, mixed-methods methodology to conduct the SWOT analysis is described in detail in [Report on the state of the art on energy poverty and disability and relevant indicators](#) (D2.1).

Figure 10: Library overview

The resources are grouped into five main topics:

- Energy Poverty
- Gender

- Disability
- Energy Efficiency
- Summer Energy Poverty

Each thematic area has a **short explanation** to help users understand what they will find therein.

Energy Poverty ↗
Energy poverty means not having enough access to affordable, reliable energy like electricity or heating. People experiencing energy poverty may struggle to keep their homes warm, cook food, or use basic appliances. It affects health, comfort, and quality of life, especially during extreme weather like hot summers or cold winters.
This section gathers foundational and advanced resources that explore the concept of energy poverty, its causes, consequences, and policy responses. You will find materials that define energy poverty, explain its impact on different populations, and provide strategies for identification and mitigation. Resources are organized alphabetically and include tools, reports, training materials, and courses targeting municipalities, citizens, and intermediaries.

Gender ↗
Gender refers to the roles, behaviors, and identities that society associates with being male, female, or other. It goes beyond biological differences and includes how people see themselves and express who they are. Gender can vary between cultures and individuals.
This section focuses on the gendered dimensions of energy poverty. It highlights how women and gender-diverse individuals are uniquely affected by energy poverty and explores inclusive approaches to policy and service delivery. Resources are arranged alphabetically and include gender-sensitive guidelines, training materials, and case studies aimed at various target groups.

Disability ↗
A disability is a physical, mental, or emotional condition that makes certain activities or tasks harder for a person. Disabilities can affect how someone moves, sees, hears, thinks, or interacts with the world. People with disabilities may need extra support or accommodations to do everyday needs.
Here you will find materials addressing how energy poverty intersects with physical disability. This section includes resources that explore the specific barriers people with disabilities face in accessing energy and how these challenges impact health, mobility, and quality of life. Resources are alphabetized and tailored to support municipalities, intermediaries, and citizens in creating inclusive, accessible responses.

Energy Efficiency ↗
Energy efficiency means using less energy to do the same task. It helps save money and reduce waste by making buildings, appliances, and vehicles work better without using extra power. For example, energy-efficient light bulbs use less electricity but give the same amount of light.
This section focuses on improving energy efficiency as a key strategy to reduce energy poverty. It includes practical tools, technical guidelines, and educational materials that explain energy-saving measures and support sustainable housing upgrades. Resources are listed alphabetically and include content suitable for municipalities, intermediaries and citizens.

Summer Energy Poverty ↗
Summer energy poverty happens when people cannot afford enough energy to keep their homes cool during hot weather. This can make it hard to use fans or air conditioning, leading to discomfort and health risks, especially for vulnerable groups like the elderly or children.
This section addresses the less-known but critical issue of summer energy poverty. It includes reports, training materials, and adaptive strategies for heat resilience, especially for vulnerable populations. Resources are organized alphabetically and support all target audiences in understanding and addressing this seasonal risk.

Figure 11: Library categories

Inside each topic, materials are listed in alphabetical order.

Different types of resources are included:

1. Training Materials
2. Training Courses
3. Tools
4. Reports
5. Guidelines

Each resource is also tagged according to its intended audience — **Municipalities, Intermediary Associations** or **Citizens**.

Disability

Course Settings Participants Grades Reports More

Disability

Collapse all

A **disability** is the result of the interaction between people living with impairments and barriers in the physical, attitudinal, communication and social environment. For example, it is not the inability to walk that keeps a person from entering a building by themselves, but the stairs that are inaccessible to them. A disability is socially constructed as a disadvantage or restriction of activity caused by a society which takes little or no account of people who have impairments and thus excludes them from mainstream activity. Here you will find **materials** addressing how energy poverty intersects with physical disability. This section includes resources that explore the specific barriers people with disabilities face in accessing energy and how these challenges impact health, mobility, and quality of life. Resources are **alphabetized and tailored** to support municipalities, intermediaries, and citizens in creating inclusive, accessible responses.

Training course on co-designing accessible resources

This training program provides guidance on collaboratively designing educational courses that are accessible to people with disabilities. It covers inclusive design principles, stakeholder involvement, and practical strategies to ensure accessibility. (2022)

Language: English

Target: intermediaries

Type of document: training course

Training course on human rights and disability

This training program by the Council of Europe focuses on human rights related to disability. It covers legal frameworks, rights protection, and inclusive practices to support persons with disabilities. (2024)

Language: English

Target: municipalities, citizens

Type of document: training course

0

Figure 12: Example of Resources on Disability

6. Accessibility

6.1 Accessible design

The ASSERT Academy has been designed with accessibility at its core. To ensure that all learners — including those with disabilities — can fully benefit from the training, the platform adopts a simple, intuitive, and user-friendly structure. Its straightforward layout, clear language, and essential-only content are intentional choices that help remove barriers and make the learning experience inclusive, effective, and accessible to the widest possible audience.

Moodle LMS is WCAG 2.1 AA compliant, meaning that Moodle meets the respective accessibility criteria. Whether you are an educator, learner, developer, or system administrator, Moodle LMS authoring and evaluation tools are endorsed by WCAG as perceivable, operable, understandable, and compatible.

All design and layout choices were informed by evaluations carried out through [a dedicated platform developed by the Italian National Research Council \(CNR\)](#), which assesses the accessibility of websites and digital documents according to the international WCAG guidelines defined by the International Web Association. To ensure full visual accessibility, AISFOR applied a colour checker to calculate adequate contrast ratios between foreground and background elements, improving readability for users with visual impairments. In addition, since many users rely on screen readers or text-to-speech (TTS) software to navigate digital environments, all materials were structured to ensure compatibility with assistive technologies. Moodle, the open platform used for hosting training modules, offers built-in accessibility features, including optimized navigation flows and an essential “skip-to-content” function, enabling people with low vision or blindness to access information seamlessly. Through these measures, AISFOR ensures that training resources and policy tools are inclusive, usable, and accessible to all stakeholders, including the most vulnerable groups.

6.2 Accessibility plugin

An accessibility plugin that allows users to customize the visual appearance of a Moodle to suit individual preferences appears throughout the Moodle site on all pages (including the login page) as an accessibility symbol button in the lower-right corner of the page. Clicking on the button produces a panel that contains the widgets that are available on the site. The base pack of widgets includes widgets for text colour, background colour, font face, font size, kerning, letter spacing, line height, link highlighting and image visibility. The colour widgets are designed to let the user choose their preferred colours without being restricted to a small selection of palettes.

Figure 13: Accessibility Button

Assert Consortium

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/10/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** LIFE-2023-CET **Coordinator:** AISFOR SRL (AISFOR)